

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Austrian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research

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Md. Anwar Hossain

**School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick,
Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia**

(enr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com); 10 May 2024.

Searching researcher to pursue Master Degree by research

Dr. Md. Anwar Hossain is searching researcher to pursue PhD degree or Post doctoral degree or Master Degree by research or Master of Philosophy by research or Master of Technology by research or Master of Science & Engineering by research and hunting research fund in international platform. How to promote a researcher from a trainee researcher? Every researcher needs primary care to build research career in a research care centre. Dr. Md. Anwar Hossain is professionally nursing researcher to build research career. He is also working for research and development (R&D) of research career/teaching career/professor career.

Online Publication: 6 June 2024

Keynote

The key principles of researchers for Master degree are proposed by Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist. 1100–2200-point policy has been proposed for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher for Master degree by research. The quality criteria of a master category researcher may function as guideline for the impact factor or maturity index to certify impact factor.

Keywords

Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

1100–2200-point policy, impact factor or quality index, Master degree.

Research is a very challenging career. Research is a very time-consuming journey in profession. There is a matter of self-challenge, self-investment, self-achievement, self-interest, self-motivation, self-patience, self-ethics, self-discipline, self-learning, self-dedication and self-satisfaction. In general, multidimensional criteria are being highlighted for the research career. For example: 1100–2200-point policy may be established under the categories mentioned in Table1. Both plus (+) and minus (-) point can be considered for the point calculation policy.

Table 1. Proposed specimen points for the calculation of an impact factor to admit/appoint researcher for Master degree by Research

Numbers	Key parameters for impact factor	Proposed specimen points for impact factor or quality index	Remarks for Master degree by research
1.	Quality of academic teaching (Bachelor, Master, PhD)	50-100	Not required but creditable
2.	Year of full-time teaching	50-100	Not required but creditable
3.	Year of full-time research	50-100	Not required but creditable
4.	Number of research project supervision	50-100	Not required but creditable
5.	Number of affiliated research organization in service time	50-100	Not required but creditable
6.	Research ethics & self-standard	50-100	Required
7.	Assessment of self-ethics & self-standard	50-100	Required

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8.	Research contribution in general	50-100	Not required but creditable
9.	Research publications by article or book	50-100	Not required but creditable
10.	Conference participation	50-100	Not required but creditable
11.	Number of research scholarship	50-100	Not required but creditable
12.	Number of research funding (Self-funding/organization)	50-100	Not required but creditable
13.	Personal dress code, face code, hair code and self-representation in professional platform	50-100	Required
14.	Web-side quality to notify researcher community	50-100	Not required but creditable
15.	Online data information	50-100	Not required but creditable
16.	Success forecasting of research proposal	50-100	Required
17.	Sex and other behaviour compliance	50-100	Required
18.	Self-discipline	50-100	Required
19.	Invention	50-100	Not required but creditable
20.	Involvement with national and international recognised person/organization for	50-100	Required

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	research and self-development		
21.	Number of research degree or advanced degree	50-100	Not required but creditable
22.	Research review and/or Researcher/student supervision	50-100	Not required but creditable
23.	Personal study place or study room (University/organization/self-funded)	50-100	Required
24.	Medical fitness for teaching, learning and research	50-100	Required
25.	Quality of graduate and quality of university/research organization	50-100	Required
26.	Grading of ethical standard	50-100	Required
27.	Academic or professional crime	50-100	Required
28.	Duration of full-time study leave for research, learning and professional development in whole profession	50-100	Not required but creditable
29.	Number of sole-author publication in whole profession including research evidence under recognized professional experts	50-100	Not required but creditable
30.	Quality of research teaching	50-100	Not required but creditable
31.	Year of full-time field service/training in	50-100	Required

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	industry/hospital in relevant branch for medical, engineering or other relevant profession		
32.	Number of book publication or preprint or research proposal and research gate contribution	50-100	Not required but creditable
33.	Faced professional harassment for professional duty and self-record of self-overcoming history for self-development (if applicable for any candidate)	50-100	Not required but creditable
34.	Research contribution for expertise in self-subject	50-100	Required
35.	Self-capability of writing, reporting and brain-storming for the peace of mankind	50-100	Required
36.	IELTS score and medium of previous education in English	50-100	Required
37.	Quality of research proposal	50-100	Required
38.	Alignment of research proposal with academic background of candidate	50-100	Required
39.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed school	50-100	Required
40.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed supervisor	50-100	Required

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41.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed research funding (Scholarship or research project or self-funding)	50-100	Required
42.	Government and non-government permission of research & publication (if necessary)	50-100	Required
43.	Alignment of research proposal with professional background of candidate	50-100	Required
44.	Brief personal history and Expression of interest (EoI) for professional dream & motivation	50-100	Required

Research Supervision Report/Master/Syed Ekbal/SGS/RMIT/7June 2024/0001

Research supervision report for Engr. Syed Ekbal, Executive Officer, SGS Bangladesh Limited; Applicant, Master of Design by Research, RMIT University, Australia

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Date 7 June 2024
 Engr. Syed Ekbal
 Executive Officer
 SGS Bangladesh Ltd.
 Applicant, Master of Design, RMIT University, Australia

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Dear Engr. Syed Ekbal,

Thanks for your supervision proposal of Master of Design, RMIT University. Possibly we had a message communication through linkedIn. I need time to review your proposal. I am giving few statements to proceed your RMIT application.

- You have a strength of professional experience.
- You have a strength of IELTS.
- You may apply for scholarship. Self-funding study will be expensive for you.
- Scholarship proposal pulls the positive marking to the scholarship committee. Your proposal has lacking of any technical approach to study circular economy. Circular economy has multidimensional branches. For circular economy, there is also a matter of industry attachment, industry work station, industry interest & industry permission. There is also way of approaching laboratory-based work to do research on circular economy in terms of pollution and environmental impact. You may include some discussion about the pollution in dyeing and finishing if there is any impact on circular economy. You have experience in the field of textile testing. There is also scope of standardization related research proposal. Therefore, you will have less movement for data collection relates to circular economy. You mentioned the name of countries and interviews of industry peoples where you need to take permission along with physical movement for data collection. Hence, your research work should be focused to establish any specific improvement in your field of textile engineering. If you like the research on circular economy, if you understand circular economy; you will have a chance to move little bit to focus your specific improvement during your study of Master of Design. So, the way of your focus and study may be progressed gradually.
- You need to think about research fund to establish your finding of research. University may have limited fund or zero fund to collect your experimental data.
- In proposal, you need to add a diagram of your work plans. You should have a visualization of your research finding. For example: if you are going to new market and if you are planning to purchase something; accordingly, you will have a visualization and you will have a plan for your action. Every visualization identifies the broadness of pipeline to proceed your success of research.
- In your CV, you need to add brief about daily working of your present job; you need to add your permanent address, nationality, personal history, etc.
- You need to invest time to develop research proposal.
- My personal profile is being attached here if you need something about me you may e-mail me. If you need to use my name in your RMIT application form, you may write my name.

Cite

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Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection (CV of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978674>

- Please read about my personal research service and charge to develop researcher if you are enthusiastic in research career and agree to pay. This is free of cost advise on 7 June 2024, if you need next stage support, you need to go through payment option.

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Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, enr.anowar@yahoo.com. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. J. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

- If you can admit RMIT, please ask residential support from RMIT, please ask cyber security support from RMIT for your laptop and mobile device.
- Please mention reference number for your every correspondence
Research supervision Report/Master candidate/Syed Ekbal/SGS/RMIT/7June 2024/0001

The impact factor to appoint researcher for Master degree by research is assessed for Engr. Syed Ekbal, Executive Officer, SGS Bangladesh Ltd.

Assessment type: research proposal & CV

Research Title: Textiles, Circularity, and Design: Collaborative Opportunities for Sustainable Practices in the Australian and Bangladeshi Fashion and Textile Industry

Table 2. Proposed specimen points for the calculation of an impact factor to admit/appoint researcher for Master degree by Research

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1.	Quality of academic teaching (Bachelor, Master, PhD)	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
2.	Year of full-time teaching	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
3.	Year of full-time research	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
4.	Number of research project supervision	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
5.	Number of affiliated research organization in service time	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
6.	Research ethics & self-standard	50-100	Required	Not assessed
7.	Assessment self-ethics & self-standard	50-100	Required	Not assessed
8.	Research contribution in general	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
9.	Research publications by article or book	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
10.	Conference participation	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
11.	Number of research scholarship	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
12.	Number of research funding (Self-funding/organization)	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
13.	Personal dress code, face code, hair code and self-representation in professional platform	50-100	Required	Not assessed

Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology

Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, and Postdoc)
 E-mail: engr.anwar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/>

14.	Web-side quality to notify researcher community	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
15.	Online data information	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
16.	Success forecasting of research proposal	50-100	Required	50
17.	Sex and other behaviour compliance	50-100	Required	Not assessed
18.	Self-discipline	50-100	Required	Not assessed
19.	Invention	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
20.	Involvement with national and international recognised person/organization for research and self-development	50-100	Required	0
21.	Number of research degree or advanced degree	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
22.	Research review and/or Researcher/student supervision	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
23.	Personal study place or study room (University/organization/self-funded)	50-100	Required	Not assessed
24.	Medical fitness for teaching, learning and research	50-100	Required	Not assessed
25.	Quality of graduate and quality of university/research organization	50-100	Required	70

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PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
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Research Address: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University,
 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:**
 engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

26.	Grading of ethical standard	50-100	Required	Not assessed
27.	Academic or professional crime	50-100	Required	Not assessed
28.	Duration of full-time study leave for research, learning and professional development in whole profession	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
29.	Number of sole-author publication in whole profession including research evidence under recognized professional experts	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
30.	Quality of research teaching	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
31.	Year of full-time field service/training in industry/hospital in relevant branch for medical, engineering or other relevant profession	50-100	Required	70
32.	Number of book publication or preprint or research proposal and research gate contribution	50-100	Not required but creditable	0
33.	Faced professional harassment for professional duty and self-record of self-overcoming history for self-development (if applicable for any candidate)	50-100	Not required but creditable	0

Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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 E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264; Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/>

34.	Research contribution for expertise in self-subject	50-100	Required	0
35.	Self-capability of writing, reporting and brain-storming for the peace of mankind	50-100	Required	0
36.	IELTS score and medium of previous education	50-100	Required	75
37.	Quality of research proposal	50-100	Required	50
38.	Alignment of research proposal with academic background of candidate	50-100	Required	75
39.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed school	50-100	Required	80
40.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed supervisor (Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain)	50-100	Required	80
41.	Alignment of research proposal with proposed research funding (Scholarship or research project or self-funding)	50-100	Required	70
42.	Government and non-government permission of research & publication (if necessary)	50-100	Required	0
43.	Alignment of research proposal with professional background of candidate	50-100	Required	60
44.	Personal history versus	50-100	Required	Not assessed

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
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Research Address: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University,
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 engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

45.	Brief personal history and Expression of interest (EoI) for professional dream & motivation	50-100	Required	Not assessed
-----	---	--------	----------	--------------

Anowar Hossain

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: SYED EKBAL

Cc: Andrea Eckersley, Scott Mayson, Lijing Wang, Robert Shanks, Xin Wang, Sean Ryan, alice.payne@rmit.edu.au, RMIT Connect, mac.fergusson@rmit.edu.au, SHADI HOUSHYAR, Vice Chancellor, amber.douglas@rmit.edu.au, calum DrummondHide

Fri, Jun 7 at 12:41 PM

Engr. Syed Ekbal

Executive Officer

SGS Bangladesh Ltd.
 Candidate, Master of Design, RMIT University, Australia

Dear Engr. Syed Ekbal,
 I have assessed your research proposal on 7 June 2024. I have attached the pdf report of primary assessment for your proceeding of RMIT University application and next stage action.

Please try to fulfill the dream of your higher education and research excellency of Master degree by research.

Your Honour

Best Regards for your excellency

Cite

Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Textile Engineering (Dyeing & Processing)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

(Funded by Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship)

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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enqr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, **Entrepreneur**); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Research Address since 2020

512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

Contact: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com, +8801788396264

Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/enqr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

**[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have power in terms of
presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]**

Inquiry About Research Supervision for Master of Design by Research

Yahoo/Inbox

SYED EKBAL

From: iqbaltex001@gmail.com

To: enqr.anowar@yahoo.com

Thu, Jun 6 at 12:13 AM

Dear Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain,

Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enqr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

I hope this message finds you well. My name is Syed Ekbal, and I am writing to express my interest in pursuing a Master of Design by Research at RMIT, with a particular focus on sustainable practices within the textile industry.

To provide a brief overview of my background, I currently serve as the Executive Officer at SGS Bangladesh Ltd., where I specialize in textile testing. I hold a bachelor's degree in textile engineering with a focus on Apparel Manufacturing Technology and have accumulated over five years of professional experience dedicated to ensuring the highest quality and compliance with industry standards. My passion lies in advancing sustainable practices within the textile industry, and I am eager to explore research opportunities that align with this focus.

My proposed research, titled -**Textiles, Circularity, and Design: Collaborative Opportunities for Sustainable Practices in the Australian and Bangladeshi Fashion and Textile Industry**, aims to explore the challenges and opportunities for achieving circularity and environmental sustainability in the textile sectors of Australia and Bangladesh. The research will focus on collaborative efforts between companies in both countries to address key challenges such as fast fashion, low-quality textiles, and complex supply chain structures. Additionally, the study will investigate consumer behavior in Australia related to sustainable choices and textile waste management practices in both countries.

The research will employ a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative methods (interviews, case studies) and quantitative approaches (surveys) to analyze collaborative dynamics, identify challenges, and propose strategies for a sustainable and circular supply chain. The study will also emphasize the development of a robust fiber recycling sector and explore opportunities for consumer engagement in sustainable practices like garment donation, reuse pathways, and eco-friendly washing procedures.

Given your esteemed background and extensive expertise in the field of textiles, I am seeking your guidance and potential supervision for my research. Your profound understanding of technical textiles, camouflage textiles, color engineering, and extensive contributions to the textile industry make you an ideal mentor for my study.

Could we possibly arrange a time to discuss my research proposal and the next steps for applying to the Master of Design by Research program at RMIT? I am in the process of preparing the necessary documents for the Expression of Interest as outlined on the RMIT How to Apply page.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
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Austrian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
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applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
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Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
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Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
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enr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Thank you for considering my request. I look forward to the opportunity to discuss this further and explore how my research can contribute to the field of sustainable textiles under your supervision.

Page | 17

Best regards,

Syed Ekbal

Email: iqbaltex001@gmail.com

SYED EKBAL

From: iqbaltex001@gmail.com

To: Anowar Hossain

Thu, Aug 1 at 10:42 PM

Subject: Follow-Up on Primary Assessment Report for RMIT University Application

Dear Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain,

I hope this email finds you well.

Thank you very much for assessing my research proposal and for providing the primary assessment report on 7 June 2024. I greatly appreciate your detailed evaluation and the guidance you have provided for proceeding with my RMIT University application.

I am highly motivated to pursue my Master of Design by Research at RMIT University, focusing on sustainable practices within the textile industry. Your feedback and encouragement mean a

Cite

Md. Anowar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

great deal to me, and I am determined to fulfill my dream of higher education and research excellence.

Please find attached the primary assessment report you provided. I am currently reviewing the recommendations and preparing the necessary documents for the next stage of my application.

Page | 18

However, I would like to bring to your attention that I had previously applied through the RMIT website, but my application was refused with the following reason: "Your application has been unsuccessful due to the following reason(s): Your qualification has been assessed and is not considered as comparable to an Australian Bachelor degree." Given this situation, I am eager to know if there are any alternative options available to me to address this issue and proceed with my application.

Thank you once again for your invaluable support and guidance.

Best regards,

Engr. Syed Ekbal

Executive Officer, SGS Bangladesh Ltd.

Candidate, Master of Design, RMIT University, Australia

Email: iqbaltex001@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain

From: engr.anowar@yahoo.com

To: SYED EKBAL

Fri, Aug 9 at 2:06 PM

Dear Engr. Syed Ekbal,

I am citing your RMIT application output.

"Your qualification has been assessed and is not considered as comparable to an Australian Bachelor degree."

You may attach your syllabus of your bachelor degree if you have any option to submit.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
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Austrian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
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MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission);
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia
Lecturer (study leave), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
& Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam)
Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
Trained from India: Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research Address: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University,
25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:**
enr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Thanks for your interest in admission to RMIT University. If RMIT University has any provision, I have nothing to do for the application process. If you are planning to study Australia, you may search and apply to another university in Australia.

Your Honour

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)

Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University

PhD (Fashion & Textiles); PhD Research ID: 3820066

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry

Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)

Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering

Cite

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Former Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore

Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Former Lecturer & Head, Department of Textile Engineering

Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), Newcastle University College, Chittagong

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Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

Certified Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)

International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
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PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
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**Please Visit the Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD;
Defence Scientist**

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

**[Unethical implementation of power is a global challenge, actually nobody should have
power in terms of presidentship/professorship/directorship/chairmanship, but everyone
has ethical power to serve the society all over the world]**

Research Supervision Report/PhD/Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman/Fakir Fashion Limited/27July 2025/0001

To Whom It May Concern

Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist
Manager, Design & Product Development
Fakir Fashion Limited, Dohorgaon, Rupganj, Narayanganj, Bangladesh
E-mail: asad.zamanfdt@gmail.com, mobile phone: +8801711 415459

This letter is sent to Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist for his PhD interest under the
supervision of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister
(Dr.). Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain would like to thank to Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist for his
interest in PhD research and PhD contribution. A PhD is a matter of financial investment, determination,

Cite

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policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles,
RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (enr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

dedication, patience, honesty, privacy, study and study. Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a primary scan of the academic and professional background of Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman has professional strength and experience in national and international coordination and management in his field of academic study. He is being supervised to add the following parameters for the assessment of his profile/curriculum vitae. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist need to send a brief curriculum vitae to Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). to satisfy the requirement.

1. Academic score from the secondary school certificate to BSc in Knitwear Manufacturing & Technology (full-time) and Master of Arts in Fashion Design and Technology (part-time/professional) including the student identity number in school.
2. Duration of the Master degree.
3. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist needs to submit his thesis of Master degree and BSc degree if he has any thesis/report to pursue the degree.
4. Permanent address, official address, national identity number, passport number, and relevant personal information and identity proof.
5. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist needs to submit an expression of interest (EOI). The EOI of a PhD research study may be social value, professional value, academic value, research practice, and jumping to the teaching profession. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman should submit his self-planning, self-thinking, and self-writing report for his primary assessment. The self-motivation of Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist should write around 100-500 words.
6. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist needs to read the financial requirement/one-time charge (20,000USD) of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman needs to write about his self-understanding and financial agreement. A meeting charge of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is 1000 USD.

Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o.

A. Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, enr.anowar@yahoo.com.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

7. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist needs to have a face-to-face primary meeting if he agrees with the PhD requirement of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.). The meeting charge of 1000USD should be pre-paid to the bank account of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Bank account details: Md. Anowar Hossain, saving account no: 0178 12200003933, First security Islami bank PLC, Birulia Branch, Dhaka- (Routing No: 105260808).
8. Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist may read the full profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Research Address: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anwar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

9. If Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist has any plan of research proposal, he may submit the research proposal on “bridging the skills of textile engineers between textile industry and university.” Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman remarked on relevant field in his e-mail.
10. The work experience and academic background of Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman is matching the research proposal relevant to merchandising, fashion design, product development in garments and textile, fashion engineering. Therefore, Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist may read the publications and literature reviews relevant to merchandising. A merchandiser and product developer has the scope to develop a research proposal on
 - Merchandising action and support for product development, negotiation, satisfaction with buyers and proposing international law in garment merchandising.
 - Fashion engineering for optical performance.
 - Fashion engineering for technical performance.
11. Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) had a relevant report on merchandising.

Cost Minimization in Sample Development and Approval Process by Proper Merchandising Action for kids and Ladies Garments. *Trends in Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology (Online), USA.*
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cost-Minimisation-in-Sample-Development-and-Process-Hossain-Samanta/ee6de04748b507cdec19cb7af66cfde0870a5b0d>;
<https://doi.org/10.31031/TTEFT.2018.04.000590>

12. The following online links are remarked in the profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain; Defence Scientist; Barrister (Dr.); Postdoc, PhD, MTech, and BSc Engineering in Textile Technology; Postdoc and PhD in Law.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11452.21127>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278881>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Cite

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Asad

27 July 2025

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Page | 24

ASAD ZAMAN

To: me · Fri, Jul 25 at 11:46 AM

Message Body

Dear Mr. Anowar,

I hope you are doing well.

My name is Md. Asaduzzaman **Ex VIYELLATEX**, a fashion product development professional from Bangladesh with 13+ years of industry experience working with brands like Calvin Klein, ZARA, H&M, and C&A. I'm writing to express my interest in pursuing a PhD under in the field of sustainable fashion and fashion product innovation.

With both academic and international design collaboration experience, I'm passionate about bridging industry practices with research. I've attached my CV for your kind review and would appreciate your advise to explore any relevant openings under your guidance.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Best regards,

Md. Asaduzzaman

 +8801711 415459

| asad.zamanfdt@gmail.com

Anowar Hossain

To: ASAD, Bcc: SYED · Thu, Jul 31 at 6:36 AM

Message Body

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
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Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
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army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
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Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman, Fashion Technologist

Manager, Design & Product Development

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E-mail: asad.zamanfdt@gmail.com, mobile phone: +8801711 415459

Dear Mr. Md. Asaduzzaman,

I have attached a pdf file for your record of PhD interest and action.

Your Honour; Please Pardon Me

Best Regards for your excellency

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist

PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh)

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Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology

University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India

BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Page | 26

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia

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Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
color engg), applied law & criminology
Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)
Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTEch,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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Chief Director & Founder (Defence Project), RMIT University, Australia
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PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.
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Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

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 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
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 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
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Cite

Md. Anwar Hossain; Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com); 6 June 2024.

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